

2D Metal Phosphorous Trichalcogenides (MPCh₃) for Sustainable Energy Storage and Conversion: Nanoarchitectonics and Advanced Applications

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2D metal phosphorous trichalcogenides (MPCh₃) have attracted considerable attention in sustainable energy storage and conversion due to their distinct physical and chemical characteristics, such as adjustable energy bandgap, significant specific surface area, and abundant active sites. However, research on 2D MPCh₃ primarily focuses on electrocatalysis, and understanding its energy conversion and storage mechanisms remains incomplete. This review comprehensively summarizes recent advancements in energy storage and conversion using 2D MPCh₃-based materials of various structures. It begins with a discussion of the distinctive properties and preparation techniques of 2D MPCh₃, followed by a focus on the rational design and development of these materials for diverse energy-related applications, including rechargeable batteries, supercapacitors, electrocatalysis, photocatalysis, and desalination. Finally, it outlines the key challenges and prospects for future research on 2D MPCh₃ materials.

1. Introduction

As global energy demands escalate, traditional fossil fuels fall short of meeting humanity's evolving needs.^[1-3] Concurrently, fossil fuel overconsumption precipitates energy crises and environmental degradation, thereby increasing the difficulty of achieving a sustainable carbon-neutral society.^[4,5] Consequently, the imperative arises to curtail fossil fuel usage and address environmental degradation while exploring renewable and environmentally friendly energy storage and conversion approaches to promote carbon neutrality.^[6,7] The swift progress of technologies like rechargeable batteries,^[8] supercapacitors,^[9] electrocatalysis,^[10] photocatalysis,^[11] and desalination^[12] has fostered the development of efficient energy storage and conversion systems, but also underscores the necessity for innovative materials.

In recent years, 2D materials have emerged as promising candidates in energy storage and conversion, owing to their distinct physical and chemical traits like high specific surface area, abundant active sites, and good electronic conductivity.^[13-15] Beyond graphene, extensive research has delved into various 2D materials such as transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs),^[16] transition metal oxides (TMOs),^[17] MXenes,^[18] layered double hydroxides (LDHs),^[19] and black phosphorus (BP).^[20] While these materials exhibit commendable performance in specific aspects, they are constrained by factors like low electron conductivity, poor air stability, and potentially hazardous or toxic preparation processes, limiting their broader applications.^[21-23] Hence, the development of novel 2D materials holds significant promise for advancing energy storage and conversion technologies.

Metal-phosphorus-chalcogen (MPCh_x) complexes have been increasingly recognized for their broad potential applications, particularly in the domain of 2D metal phosphorous trichalcogenides (MPCh₃), which are represented by the general chemical formula MPCh₃ (where M = Ni, Fe, Zn, etc., and Ch = S and Se).^[24-26] Each atomic layer comprises two atomic units, also known as M₂P₂Ch₆.^[27,28] Unlike the widely explored TMDs materials, the bandgap of MPCh₃ materials is influenced by different metal elements, and the interlayer forces between their nanosheets are van der Waals forces or weak covalent bonds,

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Figure 1. Schematic diagram of the use of 2D MPCh₃ nanosheets and their unique physical and chemical properties for energy conversion and storage.

which endow them with more diverse physical and chemical properties. While research on MPCh₃ is still in its early stages, existing review articles predominantly focus on electrocatalysis, notably water electrolysis.^[29,30] However, there is a critical need to explore further the advancements of MPCh₃ in rechargeable batteries, supercapacitors, photocatalysis, and photothermal conversion, as well as to deepen our understanding of their roles and mechanisms in energy storage and conversion processes. There is also a review on MPCh₃ in the field of energy storage and conversion,^[31] but it lacks timeliness and has limited applications. Therefore, it is essential to promptly summarize the latest research progress on MPCh₃ in the field of energy storage and conversion, providing potential guidance for the development of next-generation high-performance energy materials and technologies.

For fabrication and synthesis, the concept of nanoarchitectonics can be adopted here to guide the synthesis of 2D MPCh₃ nanomaterials and the related nanocomposites and to guide the tailoring of the structural features. Nanoarchitectonics was proposed as a post-nanotechnology concept to build and construct functional material systems by architecting atoms, molecules, and nanomaterials as building blocks.^[32] The 2D MPCh₃ materials, which have various types of metal atoms, adjustable energy bandgap, different interlayer forces, etc., can be consid-

ered a great material system for nanoarchitectonics. In this review article, our primary focus is on the fabrication and synthesis methods and applications of 2D MPCh₃ nanosheets in the realms of energy conversion and storage. Initially, we explore the physicochemical properties and preparation techniques of MPCh₃ nanosheets. Then, different synthesis methods are briefly introduced. Subsequently, building upon these properties, we provide a comprehensive summary of their research advancements in rechargeable batteries, supercapacitors, photocatalysis, electrocatalysis, and desalination (**Figure 1**). Lastly, we address the current primary challenges and future prospects associated with 2D MPCh₃ nanosheets in the domain of energy storage and conversion. To summarize, 2D materials, especially 2D MPCh₃ materials, have great and abundant diversities and tailorabilities, which endow them with promising applications in the field of sustainable energy storage and conversion.

2. Physicochemical Properties and Synthetic Strategies

2.1. Physicochemical Properties

Figure 2a displays the metal elements from the periodic table known to form MPCh₃-type materials.^[29] The unique crystalline

Figure 2. a) The composition of metal atoms and their valence states in the $MPCh_3$ crystal from the periodic table of elements. b) The top and side views of the crystalline structures of $NiPS_3$ and $SnPS_3$. Reproduced with permission.^[33] Copyright 2023, Wiley-VCH GmbH. c) The top and side views of the crystalline structures of $AgInP_2S_6$. Reproduced with permission.^[34] Copyright 2021, Springer Nature.

structure of $MPCh_3$ compounds enables them to fulfill distinct roles in energy storage and conversion. Generally, $MPCh_3$ materials can be categorized into two types based on their interlayer interactions.^[33] One type involves P_2 pairs and metal atoms in octahedral coordination, capable of stacking into layered structures through van der Waals forces (e.g., $NiPS_3$, $FePS_3$, $ZnPS_3$). Along the c -axis, interlayer bonding between adjacent atomic planes occurs via van der Waals interactions. This relationship typically correlates positively with the M atomic radius, with selenide compounds typically exhibiting larger interlayer spacings compared to sulfide counterparts. The other type involves P_2 pairs and metal atoms in octahedral and trigonal prismatic coordination, forming non-layered structures through contacts between $P_2S_6^{4-}$ anions (e.g., $SnPS_3$ and $PbPS_3$). The exposed metal atoms in the exfoliated non-layered material serve as active sites beneficial to catalytic reactions, as discussed further below. As illustrated in Figure 2b, this results in some metal atoms positioned centrally within sandwich-like structures (e.g., $NiPS_3$), while others are exposed on the surface of nanosheets (e.g., $SnPS_3$), offering diverse

application prospects in energy storage and conversion. $MPCh_3$ materials are also categorized into homogeneous $M_2^{II}P_2Ch_6$ and heterogeneous $M^I M^{II} P_2 Ch_6$ or $M^I M^{III} P_2 Ch_6$ based on cation species. Figure 2c exhibits the crystalline structures of $AgInP_2S_6$, showing significantly enhanced catalytic selectivity following sulfur defects engineering.^[34] Song's group combined the concepts of 2D materials and high-entropy alloys (HEAs) to prepare 2D high-entropy $Co_{0.6}(VMnNiZn)_{0.4}PS_3$ nanosheets for enhancing the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER), which greatly improved the application potential of $MPCh_3$ in the field of energy storage and conversion.^[35]

Most $MPCh_3$ materials display semiconductor electronic properties with wide bandgaps, typically falling within the range of 1.3 to 3.5 eV.^[36] The bonding between the metal cations and the $P_2S_6^{4-}$ anions is primarily ionic, and the bandgap size is highly influenced by the presence of the metal cations. Upon exfoliation into monolayers or a few layers, structural defects, and direct bandgaps emerge, introducing unique electronic characteristics, as well as anisotropy and interlayer interactions.

Figure 3. CVT for fabricating bulk $MPCh_3$ crystals. a) Schematic image of the experimental setup for preparing bulk $MPCh_3$ (MPX_3) crystals. As-prepared bulk (b1)–(b7) $NiPS_3$, $FePS_3$, $MnNiPS_3$, $FePSe_3$, $CdPS_3$, $MnPSe_3$, $ZnPS_3$ crystals. Reproduced with permission.^[41] Copyright 2016, American Chemical Society. As-prepared bulk (c1) $MgPS_3$ and (c2) $MgPSe_3$ crystals. Reproduced with permission.^[43] Copyright 2022, Wiley-VCH GmbH. As-prepared bulk (d1) $AgScP_2S_6$ and (d2) $CuScP_2S_6$ crystals. Reproduced with permission.^[42] Copyright 2023, Wiley-VCH GmbH.

In $MPCh_3$, where Ch primarily consists of S and Se, current reports on $MPCh_3$ materials in energy storage and conversion predominantly concentrate on MPS_3 . For a given metal cation, the bandgap in selenide is typically smaller than that in sulfide due to the alteration in relative electronegativity. Additionally, in comparison to MPS_3 , $MPSe_3$ generally exhibits a higher oxidation potential for the first anodic process in most cases, indicating that $MPSe_3$ can be regarded as relatively more stable.^[37,38] Therefore, $MPSe_3$ presents considerable potential awaiting further exploration in scientific research.

2.2. Synthesis Strategies

2.2.1. Chemical Vapor Transport

Most bulk $MPCh_3$ crystals are synthesized via a chemical vapor transport (CVT) method (Figure 3a).^[34,38,39] In a typical CVT growth procedure, the synthesis of bulk $MPCh_3$ occurs in a double-temperature zone furnace, where stoichiometric amounts of metal, phosphorus, and chalcogens are vaporized and reacted in a high-temperature zone; then, they are trans-

ported into a low-temperature zone for crystallization and deposition in a fused silica ampoule.^[40] During this process, the heating rate and degree of vacuum played significant roles in the crystalline quality and defect density of the bulk $MPCh_3$. As illustrated in Figure 3b, Du et al. synthesized diverse $MPCh_3$ bulk crystals utilizing the CVT technique. CVT can achieve high fidelity and extensive production of $MPCh_3$ materials.^[41] In addition, Prof. Rui Gusmão's group also prepared bulk $MgPS_3$ and $MgPSe_3$ crystals and bulk $AgScP_2S_6$ and $CuScP_2S_6$ alloy crystals by the CVT technique (Figure 3c).^[42,43] The CVT method presents challenges in regulating the extent of longitudinal growth during synthesis, thereby impeding the attainment of monolayer or few-layer materials. However, the CVT method can be used to prepare a large number of $MPCh_3$ bulk crystals, which provides conditions for liquid-phase exfoliation (LPE), mechanical exfoliation, and electrochemical exfoliation.

2.2.2. Liquid Phase Exfoliation

LPE emerges as a notably cost-effective method for producing large-scale ultrathin 2D $MPCh_3$ nanosheets from bulk

Figure 4. Schematic illustration of the process of fabricating MPCh_3 nanosheets. a) Bulk MPCh_3 crystals. b) Intercalated bulk MPCh_3 crystals. c) Exfoliated MPCh_3 nanosheets. d) Mechanical exfoliation tape on the bulk MPCh_3 crystals. e) Schematic of the experimental setup for electrochemical intercalation exfoliation.

crystals. In a typical LPE process (Route 1, as depicted in Figure 4a,c), the MPCh_3 bulk crystals are dispersed into suitable solvents.^[33,42,44–50] Following this, the bulk crystals undergo grinding to yield the corresponding nanosheets. After undergoing ultrasonication treatment, MPCh_3 nanosheets with the desired thickness and size can be collected via centrifugation. Using ethanol, acetone, and isopropanol as solvents, successful preparation of CoPS_3 , NiPS_3 , and SnPS_3 nanosheets with ultrathin thickness has been achieved through the LPE method.^[33] Furthermore, exfoliation of bulk FePS_3 in a hydrazine solution has led to the production of monolayered FePS_3 quantum sheets with diameters ranging from 4 to 8 nm, displaying enhanced photocatalytic properties for highly efficient hydrogen generation.^[51] Additionally, other MPCh_3 nanosheets, such as MnPS_3 ,^[39] could also be synthesized using the LPE method.

2.2.3. Mechanical Exfoliation

The methods employed to produce MPCh_3 nanoflakes through mechanical means can be categorized into micromechanical exfoliation and ball milling techniques.^[29–30,52] These methods counteract the van der Waals forces between adjacent layers of MPCh_3 by utilizing normal and shear forces, respectively. Micromechanical exfoliation involves gradually separating layered bulk crystals into few-layered or monolayer nanosheets (Route 2, as illustrated in Figure 4a,d,c), facilitated by either

transparent tape or external mechanical forces. The dissociation and generation energies associated with lamellar MPCh_3 materials are comparatively lower than those of conventional 2D materials, making the exfoliation process thermodynamically favorable. Since only physical alterations occur during micromechanical exfoliation, it can be seen as a non-destructive technique conducive to maintaining a pristine surface state.

Ball milling is widely used in powder production and is known for its effectiveness compared to micromechanical exfoliation.^[53–55] In the ball milling apparatus, two main mechanisms induce exfoliation and fragmentation effects. The first mechanism involves shear forces, which are particularly effective for obtaining large-scale MPCh_3 sheets. The second mechanism involves collision or vertical impact caused by the ball during the rolling process, leading to the fracturing of large flakes into smaller ones. This can compromise crystalline integrity and facilitate the formation of amorphous or non-equilibrium phases. Comparative analysis shows a reduction in the lateral dimensions of MPCh_3 nanosheets when using ball milling.^[56]

2.2.4. Electrochemical Exfoliation

Many existing preparation methods face challenges such as uncontrolled thickness, uneven topography and area

Figure 5. CVD of MPCh₃ nanosheets. a) Schematic image of the experimental setup for preparing MPCh₃ (MPX₃) nanosheets. Atomic force microscopy (AFM) images of the as-prepared b–e) Ni_{0.68}Co_{0.32}PS₃, In_{2/3}PS₃, SnPS₃, and MnPS₃ nanosheets. Reproduced with permission.^[40] Copyright 2021, American Association Advancement Science. Reproduced with permission.^[60] Copyright 2018, Wiley-VCH GmbH. Reproduced with permission.^[61] Copyright 2021, American Chemical Society. Reproduced with permission.^[62] Copyright 2022, American Chemical Society. f1–f8) Optical microscopy (OM) images of the CdPS₃, NiPS₃, CoPS₃, VPS₃, Mn_xCo_{1-x}PS₃, Mn_xFe_{1-x}PS₃, Fe_xCd_{1-x}PS₃ and Mn_xFe_yCd_{1-x-y}PS₃ nanosheets. Reproduced with permission.^[63] Copyright 2023, Springer Nature.

distribution, prolonged processing durations, and inadequate quality. In contrast, the electrochemical exfoliation method (Route 3, as illustrated in Figure 4a,e,c) is typically conducted under mild conditions, resulting in large-scale monolayer MPCh₃ with superior quality, crystallinity, and yield.^[57] Jan Luxa and his/her co-authors explored the degree of exfoliation with respect to the applied bias between the anode and cathode in an electrochemical exfoliation cell. The exfoliation voltage ranged from -2.8 to -3 V vs. Ag/AgCl reference electrode in a closed glovebox with an inert gas as the protective gas. The results showed that more negative bias will lead to a higher degree of exfoliation, resulting in higher electrocatalytic H₂ production activity.^[58] In addition, the conductivity, defect density, and thick-

ness of the exfoliated 2D material can be adjusted by varying the electrochemical parameters (voltage/current) or electrolyte. Additionally, the extent of exfoliation is strongly influenced by the applied potential; generally, more negative potentials lead to more thorough exfoliation.

2.2.5. Chemical Vapor Deposition

Chemical vapor deposition (CVD) (Figure 5a) is an effective method for directly fabricating MPCh₃ nanosheets on certain specific substrates for emerging energy applications.^[38,59] In the process of synthesizing MPCh₃ nanosheets through chemical

Table 1. Recent literature reports on the performance of rechargeable batteries using 2D MPCh₃ nanosheets.

Materials	Energy storage systems	Initial capacity [mAh g ⁻¹]	Cycle number	Capacitance retention [%]	Ref.
NiPS ₃	LIBs	≈1000 at 100 mA g ⁻¹	150	79.6	[66]
Co _{0.5} Ni _{0.5} PS ₃ @G	LIBs	≈600 at 500 mA g ⁻¹	500	76	[67]
Zn _x Co _{1-x} PS ₃ /CoS ₂	LIBs	≈1000 at 200 mA g ⁻¹	100	79.4	[68]
Fe _{0.63} Co _{0.37} PS ₃ /NC	LIBs	991 at 1000 mA g ⁻¹	280	80.8	[69]
FePS ₃ /nanocellulose	LIBs	1388.7 at 1000 mA g ⁻¹	200	30.2	[70]
FePS ₃ @MXene	SIBs	746.4 at 100 mA g ⁻¹	90	90.6	[71]
FePS ₃ nanosheets@N-doped carbon	SIBs	544 at 1000 mA g ⁻¹	800	51.7	[72]
Sn ₂ P ₂ S ₆ (SnPS ₃)	SIBs	376 at 2000 mA g ⁻¹	2000	81	[73]
FePS ₃	LSBs	1080 at 1000 mA g ⁻¹	1000	53.5	[74]

vapor deposition, specific amounts of metal precursors, sulfur powder, and phosphorus powder are placed in two ceramic boats; one holds the metal precursors, and the other contains sulfur and phosphorus powders.^[40,60–63] The fabrication process typically occurs in two stages. Initially, metal precursors are obtained using the hydrothermal method or other techniques. Subsequently, these precursors, along with a mixture of sulfur and phosphorus powders, are placed in a high-temperature furnace for heat treatment. The vapors of sulfur and phosphorus react with the metal precursors to produce MPCh₃ nanosheets on the appropriate substrates.^[61] For example, the CVD of SnPS₃ nanosheets on carbon cloth substrate was via a two-step process.^[61] First, SnS₂ nanosheets were grown on carbon cloth through the solvothermal method. Then, sulfur powder and phosphorus powder were transferred into a quartz tube and placed at a low-temperature zone (T1 = 320 °C, Figure 5a) for the generation of sulfur vapor and phosphorus vapor, and as-prepared SnS₂ as Sn precursor was put at the high-temperature zone (T2 = 350 °C, Figure 5a). Finally, SnPS₃ nanosheets were synthesized. Compared to the CVT method, this approach is rapid, straightforward, and capable of producing large-size single-crystal nanosheets and alloy nanosheets, such as Ni_xCo_{1-x}PS₃, In_{2/3}PS₃, SnPS₃, MnPS₃, CdPS₃, NiPS₃, CoPS₃, Mn_xCd_{1-x}PS₃, Mn_xFe_{1-x}PS₃, Fe_xCd_{1-x}PS₃, and Mn_xFe_yCd_{1-x-y}PS₃ (Figure 5b–f).

2.2.6. Other Methods

Among synthesis methods, the hydro(solvo)thermal method is considered a cost-effective strategy for producing large-scale 2D MPCh₃ nanomaterials.^[64] This involves placing the reactant precursor into a reactor to react at high temperatures for a specified duration. By managing the amount of precursor, reaction time, and solvent type, one can control the morphology, size, thickness, defects, and crystalline phase of the 2D material. Simultaneously, the 2D products obtained are easily dispersed in organic solvents or water, making them suitable for various liquid phase applications. Although this method has limitations, such as the potential for increased defects, these defects can enhance the density of catalytic active sites, which may improve catalytic performance to some extent.^[31,65] Therefore, it is crucial to tailor applications to the specific properties required. Additionally, the salt template-assisted method can also produce high-quality FePS₃ nanosheets.^[59]

3. Applications in Sustainable Energy Storage

3.1. Rechargeable Batteries

Due to their adaptable compositions and distinct 2D structures, MPCh₃ compounds hold promise for energy storage applications. Nonetheless, the performance of bulk MPCh₃ materials has been constrained. In this regard, fabricating 2D MPCh₃ nanosheets emerges as one of the most promising strategies to tackle this challenge. With fewer layers, active sites of MPCh₃ become exposed, thereby enhancing electronic conductivities. Moreover, the low energy barrier and ample ion diffusion pathways of MPCh₃ nanosheets enable swift electron transport. These 2D MPCh₃ materials have been effectively deployed in lithium-ion batteries (LIBs), sodium-ion batteries (SIBs), lithium-sulfur batteries (LSBs), and zinc-air batteries (ZABs). The distinct roles of 2D MPCh₃ nanosheets in energy storage systems are summarized in Table 1.

3.1.1. Lithium-Ion Batteries

Different types of 2D MPCh₃ nanosheets are utilized as anode materials for LIBs. Yan et al. utilized the LPE technique to extract ultrathin few-layer NiPS₃ nanosheets from bulk-layered crystals, employing them for both the oxygen evolution reaction (OER) and LIBs as anodes (Figure 6a).^[66] They achieved a stable reversible capacity of 796.2 mA hg⁻¹ after the 150th cycle at a current density of 100 mA g⁻¹. Moreover, by utilizing Co_{0.5}Ni_{0.5}(OH)₂ nanoneedles as precursors, Co_{0.5}Ni_{0.5}PS₃ produced through a solid-state transformation (SST) process was successfully attached to graphene surfaces (Figure 6b).^[67] This resulting 0D–2D nanohybrid demonstrated exceptional cycling stability and rate performance in lithium-ion storage (Figure 6c). Wu et al. engineered a Zn_xCo_{1-x}PS₃/CoS₂ (ZCPS/CS) anode material with a 2D/3D heterostructure via effective chemical transformation (Figure 6d).^[68] The combination of bimetallic alloying and heterostructure conferred outstanding performance for LIBs anode materials, maintaining a high capacity of 794 mA hg⁻¹ after 100 cycles at 200 mA g⁻¹ (Figure 6e), and a satisfactory capacity of 465 mA hg⁻¹ at 3.0 A g⁻¹. They subsequently synthesized a bimetallic alloy Fe_xCo_{1-x}PS₃ for LIBs anodes. Theoretical calculations confirmed that alloying with Co can reduce the band gap and lower the energy barrier for Li-ion diffusion.^[69] Recently, Wang et al. successfully fabricated FePS₃-nitrocellulose

Figure 6. 2D MPCh₃-based materials in LIBs. a) Schematic illustration of NiPS₃ nanosheets for the OER and LIBs. Reproduced with permission.^[66] Copyright 2018, Royal Society of Chemistry. b) Schematic illustration of the synthesis process for Co_{0.5}Ni_{0.5}PS₃/G nanohybrids. c) Galvanostatic charge–discharge (GCD) profiles for the long-term cycling results at a current density of 500 mA g^{−1}. Reproduced with permission.^[67] Copyright 2018, Elsevier B.V. d) SEM element maps of Zn, Co, S, and P in ZCPS/CS. e) Cycling performance of the ZCPS/CS and CPS/CS electrodes at a current density of 200 mA g^{−1}. Reproduced with permission.^[68] Copyright 2022, Wiley-VCH GmbH. f) Cyclic performance and coulombic efficiency of FePS₃ and FePS₃-NC at a current density of 0.1 C. Reproduced with permission.^[70] Copyright 2023, Wiley-VCH GmbH.

(NC) electrodes with a 3D network structure.^[70] The abundant hydroxyl groups of NC exhibited stronger electrostatic interaction with lithium-ions, facilitating rapid lithium-ion adsorption. The initial capacity of FePS₃-NC was 1388.7 mAh g^{−1} at 0.1 C (100 mA g^{−1}). After 200 cycles, the coulombic efficiency of the FePS₃-NC electrode reached 99.2%, with the capacity maintained above 371 mAh g^{−1} (Figure 6f). Hence, these results deepen our understanding of the kinetic mechanism of NC in promoting rapid lithium storage in FePS₃ materials.

3.1.2. Sodium-Ion Batteries

SIBs have garnered considerable attention for their cost-effectiveness and abundant reserves, presenting promising alternatives to LIBs.^[75] In contrast to the extensive investigation of MPCh₃ nanosheets as anode materials in LIBs, research in SIBs primarily centers on FePS₃ and SnPS₃ nanosheets.

Based on the conversion reaction mechanism, FePS₃ has attracted considerable attention as a promising anode material for SIBs, offering a theoretical capacity exceeding 1300 mAh g^{−1}.^[76] Peng's team successfully synthesized a novel 2D/2D heterojunction comprising FePS₃ nanosheets@MXene nanocomposites using the LPE method, applying them in SIB anodes (Figure 7a,b).^[71] This distinctive heterojunction structure facilitates rapid reaction kinetics, mitigates volume expansion from electrode pulverization and agglomeration, suppresses the polysulfide shuttle effect, and contributes to pseudocapacitance, thereby exhibiting exceptional rate capacity and cycle stability.

Additionally, they employed the LPE method and a carbon coating approach to create few-layer FePS₃@N-doped carbon composites (Figure 7c,d).^[72] Using the high ionic conductivity and unique disulfide bonds of MPCh₃, the optimized sample demonstrates remarkable capacity performance over 800 cycles, achieving a specific capacity of 281 mAh g^{−1} at 1.0 A g^{−1} (Figure 7e). Meng et al. were the first to use Sn₂P₂S₆ (SnPS₃) bulk materials for SIBs.^[77] The results indicate that interlayer sodium-ions enhanced the pseudocapacitance of ferroelectricity, facilitating faster and easier electrochemical reactions, thereby enhancing the rate performance and cycling stability of the SnPS₃ electrode. SnPS₃ nanosheets were also synthesized using LPE, demonstrating a significantly higher dielectric constant compared to bulk SnPS₃. Even after 2000 cycles at a high rate of 2 A g^{−1}, the discharging capacity remained at 305 mAh g^{−1}, corresponding to 81% retention of the initial capacity (Figure 7f).^[73] According to the capacitance formula, increasing the dielectric constant could be a new way to increase the capacity of sodium-ions. With the assistance of 2D assembly with graphene, 2D SnPS₃ achieved more real and larger Na⁺ pseudocapacitance, thereby improving battery capacity, rate performance, and cycle stability.

3.1.3. Others Rechargeable Batteries

To date, MPCh₃ has been found to be extensively used in LIBs and SIBs and comparatively less so in other types of rechargeable batteries. However, some positive progress has still been achieved.

Figure 7. 2D MPC₃-based materials in SIBs. a) Schematic illustration of the MXene assembled on the FePS₃ nanosheet surface and the micromolecular structure. b) HRTEM images of FePS₃@MXene. Reproduced with permission.^[71] Copyright 2020, Springer Nature. c) HRTEM images of FePS₃@NC (3:1) and d) corresponding elemental mapping of C, N, Fe, P, and S. Reproduced with permission.^[72] Copyright 2022, Elsevier B.V. e) Long-term cycling performance of FePS₃@NC (4:1), FePS₃@NC (3:1) and FePS₃@NC (2:1) at 1000 mA g⁻¹. Reproduced with permission.^[77] Copyright 2018, Wiley-VCH GmbH. f) Long-term cycling performance of the few-layered Sn₂P₂S₆ battery at a current density of 2 A g⁻¹. Reproduced with permission.^[73] Copyright 2019, Elsevier B.V.

LSBs have garnered increasing attention owing to their high theoretical specific capacity (1672 mA hg⁻¹) and energy density (≈ 2600 W h kg⁻¹).^[78–80] Additionally elemental sulfur offers numerous advantages as a cathode material, including low cost and environmental friendliness. However, challenges such as sulfur's low conductivity, poor cycle stability of LSBs, and the dissolution of polysulfides leading to the shuttle effect during charging/discharging processes hinder further development. Tian's team utilized electrochemical exfoliation to prepare FePS₃ nanosheets hermetically encapsulated within hollow sulfur spheres (HSS@FePS₃) for application in LSBs (Figure 8a).^[74] Through encapsulation, soluble polysulfides can be significantly trapped, and volume expansion during discharge can be effectively accommodated. Even at a current density of 1 C, the HSS@FePS₃ cathode exhibits excellent cycling stability (Figure 8b).

ZABs have garnered significant interest due to their exceptionally high theoretical energy density, robust safety profile, and affordability.^[81–83] However, the efficiency of oxy-

gen reduction reaction (ORR) and oxygen evolution reaction (OER), serving as the discharge and charge cathode reactions of ZABs, is significantly hampered by sluggish kinetics involving four sequential proton-coupled electron transfer steps.^[84] Therefore, identifying efficient oxygen reduction/evolution electrocatalysts is paramount. Peng and collaborators synthesized ultra-thin oxygen-doped FePSe₃ (FePSe₃-O) nanosheets through Ar/O₂ plasma treatment, resulting in surface atom restructuring.^[85] This restructuring created numerous crystalline-amorphous interfaces, boosting the kinetics of the oxygen evolution reaction. As a result, the FePSe₃-O nanosheets displayed an impressively low overpotential of only 261 mV at 10 mA cm⁻², accompanied by a slight Tafel slope of 41.13 mV dec⁻¹. Exploiting these unique properties, the FePSe₃-O nanosheets were integrated as the air cathode in rechargeable liquid ZABs. These ZABs exhibited a high open-circuit potential of 1.47 V, a narrow charge–discharge voltage gap of 0.80 V, and exceptional cycling stability over 800 cycles (Figure 8c,d).

Figure 8. a) Schematic illustrations of the synthesis process of HSS@FePS₃. b) Ultralong-term cycling stability of HSS@FePS₃ at 1C. Reproduced with permission.^[74] Copyright 2020, Royal Society of Chemistry. c) Schematic illustration of the formation process and the crystal structures of the FePSe₃-O nanosheets. d) Galvanostatic cycling performance of rechargeable ZABs. Reproduced with permission.^[85] Copyright 2020, American Chemical Society.

3.2. Supercapacitor

Supercapacitors offer a higher energy density ($\approx 10 \text{ Wh kg}^{-1}$) compared to conventional capacitors, along with a greater power density ($\approx 10 \text{ kW kg}^{-1}$) and longer cycle life ($> 100\,000$ times) than secondary batteries.^[86] Typically, a supercapacitor comprises three key components: electrodes, electrolyte, and separator. Electrodes generally consist of electrode materials, binders, conductive agents, and current collectors, with electrode materials playing a pivotal role in determining electrochemical capacitor performance. Supercapacitors can be categorized into three types based on their mechanism: electric double-layer capacitors (EDLC), pseudocapacitors, and hybrid supercapacitors (Figure 9a).^[87]

Pumera's team developed a hybrid self-powered biosensor system for health monitoring by incorporating 2D NiPS₃ as the capacitive electrode.^[88] The graphene-confined NiPS₃ electrode (NiPS₃@graphene) demonstrates excellent electrochemical performance owing to its inherent 2D morphology. It maintains stable energy storage performance, with a capacity retention rate of 86% after 1000 charge–discharge cycles (Figure 9b), and exhibits good mechanical flexibility at various bending angles, retaining 97.7% of its initial performance after 500 bending cycles (Figure 9c). Zhang et al. synthesized nitrogen-doped carbon capsules (N-Cc)@NiPS_{3-x} composite electrode material in situ by hydrothermal growth of Ni(OH)_{2-x} precursor and utilizing N-Cc as the conductive substrate.^[89] The hollow N-Cc within the

Figure 9. 2D MPCh₃-based materials in supercapacitors. a) Schematic of different kinds of supercapacitors. Reproduced with permission.^[87] Copyright 2023, Wiley-VCH GmbH. b) Long-term stability of NiPS₃@rGO ZISC in terms of capacity retention and coulombic efficiency at 6.1 A g⁻¹. c) Flexibility study at different bending angles. Reproduced with permission.^[88] Copyright 2023, Elsevier B.V. d) cycling stability of the ASC device. Reproduced with permission.^[89] Copyright 2023, Elsevier B.V.

electrode material offers a larger specific surface area, providing more active sites and shorter ion transmission paths. The electrode material demonstrates a specific capacitance of 590 C g⁻¹ at a current density of 1 A g⁻¹. The assembled N-Cc@NiPS₃ 1.0//AC asymmetric supercapacitor (ASC) achieves an energy density of 55.42 Wh kg⁻¹ at a power density of 750.05 W kg⁻¹ and exhibits good stability with a retention rate of 89.9% over 8000 cycles (Figure 9d).

4. Applications in Sustainable Energy Conversion and Clean Environments

4.1. Electrocatalysis

To date, ultrathin MPCh₃ nanosheets have attracted increasing interest for use in electrocatalytic energy conversion owing to their large specific area, abundant exposed active sites, excellent electrical conductivity, low-cost raw materials, and facile preparation.^[47,52,29,64,31,90-93] Furthermore, the presence of S and P elements inhibits the oxidation of MPCh₃, thereby enhancing their stability during catalytic reactions, including HER, oxygen evolution reaction (OER), CO₂ reduction reaction (CO₂RR), oxygen reduction reaction (ORR), and N₂ reduction reaction (N₂RR) (Figure 10a). Overall, MPCh₃ nanosheets can play significant roles in clean energy generation, reducing greenhouse gas emissions, and fixing N₂.^[29]

4.1.1. Electrocatalytic Water Reduction and Oxidation

The HER and OER constitute overall water-splitting reactions, in which the HER occurs at the cathode and the OER occurs at the

anode during the electrochemical process. The electrocatalytic HER is considered the main path for H₂ energy automobiles and is one of the most promising candidates for replacing fossil energy. On the other hand, OER products can be utilized in metal-O₂ batteries for energy storage and to produce industrial hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂). Thermodynamically, it takes at least 1.23 V or 237.2 kJ mol⁻¹ Gibbs free energy to split one water molecule into one H₂ molecule and ½ O₂ molecule.^[30,54,94,95]

In acid media:

In alkaline media:

In practical electrocatalytic water splitting reactions, the potential difference (ΔE^0) or Gibbs free energy difference (ΔG^0) between the HER and OER is much larger than 1.23 V or 237.2 kJ mol⁻¹ due to the intrinsic properties of MPCh₃, the external circuit resistance, and the real reaction path. In recent years, scientists have not made efforts to prepare many MPCh₃ nanosheets and optimize their catalytic activities for HER, OER, and overall

Figure 10. MPCh₃ electrocatalysts for water reduction and oxidation. a) Schematic image of the use of MPCh₃ as an electrocatalyst. b) AFM images of the FePS₃ nanosheets. c) Raman spectra of bulk and exfoliated FePS₃. d) HER activities of catalysts under various temperature treatments and their e) corresponding EIS results. Reproduced with permission.^[45] Copyright 2019, Royal Society of Chemistry. f) Ultrathin NiPS₃ nanosheets in water. g) AFM image of NiPS₃ nanosheets. h) OER performance of NiPS₃-graphene catalysts and i) their corresponding Tafel slopes. Reproduced with permission.^[96] Copyright 2018, American Chemical Society.

water splitting. Guo's group reported a facile amine-assisted exfoliation strategy to attain few-layered FePS₃ nanosheets for efficient HER.^[45] The exfoliated FePS₃ nanosheet has a thickness of ≈ 5.69 nm (Figure 10b), which corresponds to 8 layers of the FePS₃ monolayer. Raman spectroscopy (Figure 10c) verified that the absence of the strongly infrared active E_u peak (156 cm⁻¹) in the spectrum of the nanosheets was attributed to a decrease in thickness from the bulk form to the nanosheet form. The authors measured the HER catalytic activities of FePS₃ prepared at different temperatures. Usually, the overpotential at a current density of 10 mA cm⁻² and the Tafel slope are two significant indicators used to evaluate the catalytic performance of electrocatalysts, and excellent electrocatalysts tend to have small overpotentials and small Tafel slopes. The linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) results (Figure 10d) showed that FePS₃-120 exhibited the best HER performance with the lowest overpotential of 241 mV at a current density of -10 mA cm⁻² and the smallest Tafel slope of 94 mV dec⁻¹, apart from the commercial Pt/C catalyst. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) indicated that a proper temperature (120 °C) can improve the crystallinity and thus enhance the kinetics of electron transfer within the FePS₃ nanosheets (Figure 10e). As a result, the FePS₃-120 nanosheets

exhibit superior HER performance. In addition, Song's group successfully prepared Co_{0.6}(VMnNiZn)_{0.4}PS₃ nanosheets with high-concentration active sites, which showed enhanced HER performance: an overpotential of 65.9 mV at a current density of 10 mA cm⁻² and a Tafel slope of 65.5 mV dec⁻¹.^[35]

OER, being a crucial half-reaction of electrocatalytic water splitting, has garnered extensive attention from researchers. Among the electrocatalysts, MPCh₃ nanosheets have gradually emerged as a class of high-performance OER electrocatalysts. Ren et al. reported the pure water-assisted exfoliation of NiPS₃ nanosheets and applied NiPS₃ nanosheet-graphene (NiPS₃-G) composites as highly efficient OER electrocatalysts.^[96] The NiPS₃ nanosheets, prepared in this manner, consisted of 2 to 9 individual layers of NiPS₃ (Figure 10f,g). The catalytic activity of NiPS₃-G was systematically regulated by their mass ratio. The NiPS₃-G composite materials exhibit notably enhanced OER performance due to their synergistic interactions. The refined composite denoted NiPS₃-G-1:1, demonstrated a markedly reduced overpotential of 294 mV at a current density of 10 mA cm⁻² and a decrease of 351 mV at a current density of 100 mA cm⁻², with a minimal Tafel slope of 42.6 mV dec⁻¹ (Figure 10h,i). This outstanding performance highlights the promising

potential of NiPS₃ nanosheets in combination with graphene composites as exceptionally efficient electrocatalysts for OER applications.

4.1.2. Electrocatalytic CO₂RR

The electrochemical conversion of CO₂ into various hydrocarbons, alcohols, and carboxylics via the CO₂RR is one of the most effective approaches. Since the number of detailed conversion pathways may exceed ten (see Table 2), the conversion of CO₂ into high-value-added products with high selectivity and high yield becomes critically important via an electrochemical process. Thermodynamically, CO₂ is a quite stable molecule with two strong C=O bonds (bond energy: 750 kJ mol⁻¹), meaning that it requires >sixfold energy to destroy the double C=O bonds of 1 mol of CO₂ compared with the O–H bonds of 1 mol of H₂O. Therefore, electrocatalytic CO₂ reduction is much more difficult than overall water splitting. According to Table 2, the single-electron transfer path of CO₂ reduction requires a much larger electromotive force. Therefore, multielectron transfer paths with low energy barriers can be excellent solutions for selectively producing high-value-added products during the CO₂ reduction process.

Apart from metal-based catalysts, MPCh₃ nanosheets also exhibit excellent electrocatalytic CO₂RR performance. Recently, Wang and his colleagues prepared both layered and nonlayered ultrathin MPCh₃ (such as CoPS₃, NiPS₃, and SnPS₃) nanosheets for high-performance CO₂ electroreduction catalysts by a wet grinding exfoliation approach (Figure 11a).^[33] The nanosheets obtained through exfoliation had thicknesses ranging from 2 to 3 nm (Figure 11b). The authors systematically explored the catalytic mechanism of MPCh₃ in CO₂RR. In contrast to layered nanosheets like CoPS₃ and NiPS₃, the active Sn atoms are prominently exposed on the surfaces of non-layered SnPS₃ nanosheets. As a result, these non-layered SnPS₃ nanosheets exhibit significantly enhanced catalytic activity, achieving formic acid selectivity of up to 31.6% with a current density of 7.51 mA cm⁻² at 0.65V vs. RHE (Figure 11c). This improved catalytic performance is attributed to the generation of HCOO^{*} through initial proton-electron pair addition on the SnPS₃ surface. Despite SnPS₃'s selectivity reaching 31.6%, practical applicability is limited by significant side effects. Sun's group has demonstrated that Fe₂P₂S₆ nanosheets (Figure 11d) function as effective CO₂RR electro-

catalysts, facilitating highly selective hydrogenation of CO₂ to alcohols.^[50] This catalyst achieves a high total Faradaic efficiency (FE methanol + ethanol) of 88.3%, with FE methanol reaching up to 65.2% at –0.20 V vs. RHE in a 0.5 M KHCO₃ solution, surpassing the performance of most previously reported CO₂RR electrocatalysts (Figure 11e,f). Density functional theory calculations suggest that the Fe atom on the Fe₂P₂S₆ surface serves as the active site for alcohol formation. However, exploration of other MPCh₃ catalysts in CO₂RR remains limited, necessitating substantial efforts to address this research gap.

4.1.3. Electrocatalytic N₂ Reduction Reaction

Similarly, the electrocatalytic N₂RR also involves a multistep proton-electron transfer process and multiple intermediates^[97]:

Compared with Equations (7–11), a more negative voltage means that more energy is consumed. Hence, it is difficult for the individual electron transfer paths in Equation (7) and Equation (11) to occur during the N₂RR. Picking up suitable electrocatalysts to selectively conduct the reactions shown in Equations (8, 9, and 10) has become increasingly urgent.

MPCh₃ nanosheets, known for their abundant exposed active sites, have recently attracted interest for their potential in electrocatalytic nitrogen reduction reaction (N₂RR). Lin et al. investigated the applicability of NiPS₃ nanosheets as electrocatalysts for N₂RR.^[98] They exfoliated bulk NiPS₃ crystals in various solvents (Figure 12a). Exceptional N₂RR performances were achieved by dispersing bulk NiPS₃ into bi- or trilayered nanosheets. At an applied potential of –0.4 V vs. the reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE), the production rate of NH₃ reached 118 μg h⁻¹ mg_{cat}⁻¹ with a Faraday efficiency exceeding 17% (Figure 12b,c). The N₂RR efficiency of exfoliated NiPS₃, in terms of NH₃ yield, surpasses that of numerous non-noble metal-based catalysts reported in the literature. Moreover, it maintained sustained N₂RR activity of over 90% even after multiple repetitive cycles.

4.2. Photocatalysis

In contrast to electrocatalysis, photocatalysis is a photochemical process in which the use of light energy as an external input triggers chemical reactions in solution. However, almost all electrocatalytic reactions, such as the HER, OER, CO₂RR, and N₂RR, can occur when they are carried out via photocatalysis, as shown in Figure 13a. The most significant factor is the energy band position in MPCh₃ with respect to the electrode potentials of the

Table 2. Standard electrochemical potentials for CO₂ reduction.

Half-reaction	E ⁰ /V [vs. SHE]
CO ₂ + e ⁻ → *CO ₂ ⁻	-1.91
CO ₂ + 2H ⁺ + 2e ⁻ → HCOOH(aq)	-0.61
CO ₂ + 2H ⁺ + 2e ⁻ → CO(g) + H ₂ O	-0.53
CO ₂ + 2H ⁺ + 6e ⁻ → CH ₃ OH(aq) + H ₂ O	-0.38
CO ₂ + 8H ⁺ + 8e ⁻ → CH ₄ (g) + 2H ₂ O	-0.24
2CO ₂ + 8H ⁺ + 8e ⁻ → CH ₃ COOH(aq) + 2H ₂ O	-0.30
2CO ₂ + 10H ⁺ + 10e ⁻ → CH ₃ COOH(aq) + 3H ₂ O	-0.35
2CO ₂ + 12H ⁺ + 12e ⁻ → C ₂ H ₄ (g) + 4H ₂ O	-0.34
2CO ₂ + 14H ⁺ + 14e ⁻ → C ₂ H ₆ (g) + 4H ₂ O	-0.27
3CO ₂ + 18H ⁺ + 18e ⁻ → C ₃ H ₇ OH(g) + 5H ₂ O	-0.32

Figure 11. MPCh₃ electrocatalysts for CO₂ reduction. a) The preparation route for CoPS₃, NiPS₃, and SnPS₃ nanosheets. b) AFM images of CoPS₃, NiPS₃, and SnPS₃ nanosheets. c) Faradaic efficiency of major products and current density of formic acid using SnPS₃ as an electrocatalyst. Reproduced with permission.^[33] Copyright 2023, Wiley-VCH GmbH. d) AFM images of the Fe₂P₂S₆ nanosheets. e) CO₂ reduction activity of Fe₂P₂S₆/CP in various environments. f) Faradaic efficiency of CO₂RR products on Fe₂P₂S₆ nanosheets/CP at different potentials. Reproduced with permission.^[50] Copyright 2019, American Chemical Society.

Figure 12. MPCh₃ electrocatalysts for N₂ reduction reactions. a) Photographs of exfoliated NiPS₃ in various solvents. b) LSV curves of bulk NiPS₃ and exfoliated NiPS₃ nanosheets. c) NH₃ yield of exfoliated NiPS₃ nanosheets, bulk NiPS₃, and carbon paper. Reproduced with permission.^[98] Copyright 2021, Elsevier.

Figure 13. Electron transfer number and energy band relationship diagrams. a) Schematic image of the typical electron transfer number in the photoelectrochemical OER, HER, CO₂RR, and N₂RR. b) Energy band relationship of MPC₃ with respect to electrode potentials for the CO₂RR. Reproduced with permission.^[95] Copyright 2022, American Chemical Society.

redox reactions (Figure 13b), where the conduction band (CB) position should be higher than the oxidation potential, while the valence band (VB) position needs to be lower than the reduction potential. Taking Equations (1 and 2) as examples, the CB position of MPC₃ should be >1.23 V vs. RHE so that the OER can be smoothly carried out. The VB position of MPC₃ should be <0 V vs. RHE; thus, theoretically, the HER can occur. These theories also apply to the photocatalytic CO₂RR and N₂RR.

4.2.1. Photo Electrochemical Water Reduction and Oxidation

Photoelectrochemical water splitting, which transforms solar energy into chemical energy, is an effective method for storing solar energy and significantly addresses the global energy crisis. Barua et al.^[99] successfully synthesized and characterized a variety of monometallic and bimetallic MPC₃ compounds, including MnPS₃, FePS₃, NiPS₃, ZnPS₃, CdPS₃, Ag_{0.5}In_{0.5}PS₃, MnPSe₃, FePSe₃, CdPSe₃, and Ag_{0.5}In_{0.5}PSe₃ using the CVT method. The bulk materials were exfoliated into few-layered structures through bath sonication in aqueous media, as depicted in Figure 14a,b, and employed as photocatalytic HER catalysts. Among the ternary MPS₃ and MPSe₃ compounds, NiPS₃ exhibited the most significant HER activity (2.6 mmol h⁻¹ g⁻¹, Figure 14c,d).

The photoresponsivity of synthesized M₂P₂Ch₆ compounds, for the excitation wavelength range of 385–700 nm, was evaluated for their performance in the oxygen evolution reaction (OER) under alkaline conditions.^[100] The experimentally ascertained optical bandgaps of the MPC₃ materials range from 1.5 eV for

FePSe₃ to 3.7 eV for ZnPS₃ (Figure 14e). Figure 14f displays a wide-area height profile of several flakes of exf-CoPS₃. At a potential of +1.23 V versus the reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE), MnPSe₃ demonstrates superior performance in terms of its photoelectrochemical (PEC) activity within the OER region, whereas the exfoliation of CoPS₃ enhances its PEC activity, exhibiting a twofold improvement compared to that of its bulk counterpart (Figure 14g,h).

4.2.2. Photocatalytic CO₂RR

The photocatalytic CO₂RR is termed high-efficiency solar energy utilization for relieving greenhouse effects and has gained increasing attention. Zhou and his colleagues successfully synthesized a quaternary atomic layer of AgInP₂S₆ with a thickness of ≈0.70 nm via facile ultrasonic exfoliation of the corresponding bulk crystal (Figure 14i,j).^[34] Manipulation of the sulfur defects on this atomic layer through H₂O₂ etching can significantly modulate the CO₂ photoreduction pathway, resulting in the predominant formation of ethene. A yield-based selectivity of ≈73% and an electron-based selectivity as high as ≈89% were achieved (Figure 14k,l). Computational density functional theory (DFT) calculations and in situ Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy revealed that the incorporation of sulfur vacancies in AgInP₂S₆ leads to the accumulation of charge on the silver (Ag) atoms proximal to these vacancies. As a result, the exposed Ag sites efficiently capture nascent *CO molecules, enriching the catalytic surface with important reaction intermediates. This en-

Figure 14. Photo electrocatalytic Water Reduction and Oxidation. a) SEM and b) AFM images of NiPS₃. c) HER activity of MPS₃. d) HER performance comparison with various MPS₃ materials. Reproduced with permission.^[99] Copyright 2019, Royal Society of Chemistry. e) Absorption curves of the MnPS₃ and MnPSe₃ nanosheets. f) AFM image of a CoPS₃ flake. g) MPS₃ photoanodes for the OER under 420 nm light-emitting diode illumination with a 10 s interval of light on and off. h) Typical photocurrent response at 1.23 V vs. RHE. Reproduced with permission.^[100] Copyright 2021, Wiley-VCH GmbH. i) TEM and j) AFM images of the AgInP₂S₆ single-atom layer. k) CO₂ photoreduction performance of the bulk AgInP₂S₆, AgInP₂S₆ single-atom layer, and S-vacancy-AgInP₂S₆ single-atom layer. l) Selectivity of photocatalytic CO₂ conversion for different catalysts. Reproduced with permission.^[34] Copyright 2021, Springer Nature.

richment reduces the barrier for C–C binding coupling; thus, facilitating the production of ethene.

4.2.3. Photo Reforming of plastic waste

Qiao's group realized cooperative photo redox using defect-rich chalcogenide nanosheet-coupled photocatalysts,^[101] e.g., d-NiPS₃/CdS, to achieve an ultrahigh H₂ evolution of ~40 mmol gcat⁻¹ h⁻¹ and an organic acid yield of up to 78 μmol within 9 h, together with excellent stability beyond 100 h in the photo reforming of commercial waste plastic poly(lactic acid) and poly(ethylene terephthalate) (Figure 15a,b). These metrics represent one of the most efficient plastic photo reforming metrics. In situ, ultrafast spectroscopic studies confirmed a charge transfer-mediated reaction mechanism in which d-NiPS₃ rapidly extracted electrons from CdS to boost H₂ evolution, favoring hole-dominated substrate oxidation to improve overall efficiency (Figure 15c).

4.3. Solar Desalination

In addition to being used as photocatalysts and electrocatalysts, MPCh₃ nanosheets can be applied as solar absorbers to har-

vest solar energy for photothermal solar seawater desalination. For example, Wang et al. introduced a novel approach termed mixed solvent exfoliation surface deposition (MSESD) to produce NiPS₃ nanosheets from its bulk form (Figure 16a).^[44] By applying NiPS₃/polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) onto a porous sponge, they enabled the utilization of NiPS₃ nanosheets for solar seawater desalination. These exfoliated NiPS₃ nanosheets can be as thin as 1.3 nm (Figure 16b). The resulting mixture of 10 mL NiPS₃ nanosheet combined with 1 mL of 5 wt.% PVA aqueous solution (Ni10P1-s) demonstrated a high photothermal conversion efficiency (PTCE) of 91.0% and an average PTCE of 93.5% over 10 cycle tests under 1 sun irradiation (Figure 16c,d). The excellent photothermal conversion performance is ascribed to the nonradiative photon transitions in the NiPS₃ nanosheets as well as multiple optical interactions. The solar desalination capability of other MPCh₃ materials still deserves further exploration and study.

5. Conclusions and Perspectives

In this review, we begin by providing a concise introduction to the physical and chemical characteristics of typical 2D MPCh₃ nanosheets, covering their layered and non-layered structures, plentiful metal active sites, and adjustable bandgaps. Following

Figure 15. Photo reforming of plastic waste. a) Schematic diagram of the photochemical reforming of plastic waste. b) TEM image of a defect-rich NiPS₃ (d-NiPS₃) nanosheet decorated with CdS nanoparticles. c) Organic acid products from PET for CdS, NiPS₃/CdS, and d-NiPS₃/CdS following 9 h of photo reforming. Reproduced with permission.^[101] Copyright 2023, American Chemical Society.

Figure 16. Solar desalination using MPCh₃ nanosheets. a) The preparation method of the mixed solvent exfoliation surface deposition (MSED) strategy for solar desalination. b) AFM image of a NiPS₃ nanosheet. c) Solar-to-vapor efficiency of different samples. d) Stability test of the Ni10P1-s sample. Reproduced with permission.^[44] Copyright 2024, Wiley-VCH GmbH.

Figure 17. The challenge and perspectives of 2D MPCh₃ materials in the field of energy storage and conversion.

that, we outline the various methods used for synthesizing both MPCh₃ bulk crystals and 2D MPCh₃ nanosheets, which include CVT, LPE, electrochemical exfoliation, CVD, and other techniques. Finally, we shift our focus to exploring the diverse applications of 2D MPCh₃ nanosheets in energy conversion and storage, including rechargeable batteries, supercapacitors, photocatalysis, electrocatalysis, and solar desalination.

Despite notable advancements in the synthesis and application of 2D MPCh₃ nanosheets, research on these materials remains nascent. The challenges and prospects of 2D MPCh₃ applied to energy storage and conversion are summarized in **Figure 17** as follows:

- 1) The intrinsic low electrical conductivity of MPCh₃ materials restricts their utility in energy storage and conversion. Effective strategies to enhance conductivity include forming heterojunctions with low-dimensional materials, using electron interactions, and rearranging electronic states. Moreover, functionalization and modification methods can also increase the electrical conductivity of 2D MPCh₃ nanosheets, thereby promoting their use in high-performance energy storage and conversion systems.
- 2) The stability of 2D MPCh₃ nanosheets in comparison to bulk materials requires enhancement. These nanosheets have demonstrated poor air stability, which is vital for energy storage and conversion applications. Employing organic materials other than PVA on MPCh₃ nanosheets proves to be another effective approach to enhance stability.
- 3) The practical application of MPCh₃-based energy storage devices demands focus. Energy storage initiatives using MPCh₃ materials are still confined to laboratory settings. To evaluate the full potential of MPCh₃-based materials in energy storage, it is essential to address factors such as active material loading density, power density, and structural stability during cycling. In addition, the main methods for synthesizing MPCh₃ currently include CVT and CVD. These methods face challenges in scaling up for mass production, which poses significant obstacles to their widespread practical application.
- 4) Considerable work remains on identifying catalytic active sites and understanding reaction mechanisms. Given the layered structure of metal atoms in 2D MPCh₃ nanosheets, defect engineering strategies such as vacancy creation and heteroatom doping are anticipated to enhance catalytic activity by modifying the band structure and exposing more active sites. Hence, defect engineering warrants increased focus going forward.
- 5) The controlled synthesis of 2D MPCh₃ nanosheets in terms of layer numbers and sizes requires further investigation. Although LPE is extensively employed in energy storage and conversion, achieving precise control over the layer numbers and sizes of nanosheets is challenging, with a low yield of single-layer nanosheets. Therefore, developing new efficient methods to fabricate 2D MPCh₃ nanosheets remains a challenge. Additionally, although electrochemical methods have been shown to successfully produce high-quality thin layers of NiPS₃ and FePS₃, this approach is not effective for all MPCh₃ materials. Further understanding of the delamination mechanisms of this method for these materials is required.

In summary, despite the current limitations in the performance of 2D MPCh₃ nanosheets, their unique 2D structure, adjustable bandgaps, and numerous active sites offer vast potential. While research on MPCh₃ materials is still in its initial stages, their structural regulation and performance in energy storage and conversion merit further study. This review aims to offer fundamental guidance and research concepts for scientists working with MPCh₃-based energy storage and conversion; thus, fostering advances in the field of high-performance energy storage and conversion using 2D MPCh₃ nanosheets.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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